

1 **Identifying small mammals' hairs collected with a non-invasive low-cost method on Staten**
2 **Island, New York.**

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32

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34

35 **ABSTRACT**

36 In the absence of sufficient manpower or time, hair tubes represent a humane and cost-
37 effective method for monitoring small mammal presence. We describe a methodology for
38 morphological identification of hairs collected in hair tubes placed in urban yards of Staten
39 Island using existing literature and a collection of reference hairs. Hair tubes targeted mice
40 (*Peromyscus leucopus* and *Mus musculus*), meadow voles (*Microtus pennsylvanicus*), Eastern
41 moles (*Scalopus aquaticus*), chipmunks (*Tamias striatus*), and northern short-tailed shrews
42 (*Blarina brevicauda*). We used Factor Analysis of Mixed Data and a subsequent classification
43 model to evaluate our hair classification algorithm based on hair medullary appearance, hair
44 thickness, and hair length. We observed a high correspondence between model predictions of the
45 hair identity based on reference hair and our identification methodology for all analyzed target
46 species (85% of hair samples were in agreement), except chipmunks. Hair morphology proved to
47 be a valuable technique for monitoring the distribution of small mammals in urban yards, with
48 high acceptability among homeowners. However, detailed guides for undertaking such studies
49 are still rare. We present an overview of our methodology for future use in similar studies.

50

51 **INTRODUCTION**

52 Mammalian hair structure differs among species and can be used for a variety of
53 applications, ranging from forensic diagnosis (Ahmed et al., 2018; Barksdale MA, 2017; Pilli et
54 al., 2014), to wildlife dietary studies (Shores et al., 2015; Walker et al., 2018), and non-invasive
55 small mammal monitoring (Chiron et al., 2018; Schwingel & Norment, 2010). The use of hair
56 sampling for small mammal monitoring using hair traps (Chiron et al, 2018) offers an alternative
57 to more invasive sampling strategies such as live trapping, which can be stressful for the animal
58 and require more manpower.

59 In urban ecology studies, hair traps can offer additional advantages. These non-invasive
60 traps can be more widely accepted by the public and easier to implement than live trapping
61 techniques in more urbanized areas as there are virtually no animal ethics concerns related to
62 their use and do not require frequent checking (Chiron et al, 2018). Conducting private property
63 research requires structuring questions and methods appropriately to account for the research
64 subject and the urban ecological system (Dyson et al, 2018). Hair traps reduce the imposition on
65 the homeowner by doing fewer or shorter visits and/or shifting starting times, as compared to
66 live and lethal trapping.

67 Hair traps are designed to collect mostly guard hairs, which are the thicker, protective
68 hairs forming the outside of a mammalian fur coat and can be used for species identification
69 (Mayer, 1952; Moore, 1988; Stains, 1958). The medullary pattern, cuticle scale pattern, and
70 medullary index have been established as appropriate and reliable characteristics to determine
71 the species of origin of hairs (Normandeau et al., 2018; Tridico et al., 2014). While DNA
72 analysis can be performed in some cases, it is expensive compared to hair identification using
73 hair morphology (Tridico et al., 2014).

74 As hair identification continues to gain importance in several biological fields,
75 procedures, and keys for identifying hair types using their morphological structures are helpful
76 tools. This paper aims to outline a procedure for the implementation of hair sampling in urban
77 areas and identification of mixed hair samples without a known origin and evaluate its
78 performance by comparing collected hair types in an urban area of southern New York State,
79 USA, to a reference collection. We provided descriptions for reference and collected hair types
80 that may be used to assist in other hair identification projects.

81 **METHODS**

82 *Study site*

83 Data collection took place on Staten Island, New York, USA. The island, positioned in
84 the Northern Atlantic Ocean, is a borough of New York City and is approximately sixty square
85 miles. Common small mammalian species observed on Staten Island include white-footed mice
86 (*Peromyscus leucopus*), chipmunks (*Tamias striatus*), northern short-tailed shrews (*Blarina*
87 *brevicauda*), house mice (*Mus musculus*), brown rat (*Rattus norvegicus*), meadow voles
88 (*Microtus pennsylvanicus*), eastern moles (*Scalopus aquaticus*), and grey squirrels (*Sciurus*
89 *carolinensis*). Other common medium size mammals include raccoons (*Procyon lotor*), Virginia
90 opossums (*Didelphis virginiana*), and feral cats (*Felis catus*). Land use is composed of high to
91 low-intensity development (cite NLCD) with urban forests and other green areas. Sampled yards
92 had a range of vegetation types and connectivity to green areas expected to capture a range of
93 host types.

94 *Study design*

95 This study is part of a broader study aiming at assessing human exposure to ticks and the
96 effects of urbanization on human-tick interactions. Part of this study involves household visits to

97 conduct questionnaires about behavioral risk factors and tick sampling in yards. Because small
98 mammals play a role as hosts for ticks and reservoirs for tick-borne pathogens (Pfäffle et al.,
99 2013), we conducted small mammal monitoring in yards using hair traps, a non-invasive low-
100 cost method.

101 Due to COVID-19 mitigation measures, homeowners' recruitment was conducted over
102 the phone from selected areas around major parks on Staten Island, New York. Phone lists for
103 Staten Island were purchased from InfoUSA, Inc. (<https://www.infousa.com/>), and did not
104 include phones registered in the do-not-call list. During the phone call, we explained the goals of
105 the study to homeowners and invited them to participate. An online sign-up e-form was also
106 advertised in social media and local newspapers; house visits were conducted in August 2020.
107 We measured acceptability of small mammal sampling in yards using hair traps as the proportion
108 of homeowners that accepted hair trap deployment in their yards out of those who completed our
109 phone questionnaire; compliance was measured by determining the proportion of residents who
110 participated in the questionnaire that granted us access to their yard after they expressed
111 willingness to participate. This protocol allowed us to minimize contact with homeowners in the
112 context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

113 We monitored small mammal species presence in yards using hair tubes (Chiron et al.,
114 2018). We constructed tubes from plastic sink tailpieces measuring eight inches long with a
115 diameter of one and a half inches (Figure 1). Tubes double-sided had tape (Mighty X Carpet
116 Tape, iPrimio brand) over both ends to capture hair and bait (Bamba Peanut puffs, Osem) glued
117 in the center to attract small mammals (Figure 1). Openings were 22 millimeters tall, a height
118 intended to target small insectivorous and herbivorous-granivorous or omnivorous mammals of <

119 30 g body mass, such as shrews and rodent species of the subfamilies Murinae (Chiron et al.,
120 2018).

121 **Figure 1. Hair tube used for small mammal monitoring used in this study.** (A) A hair tube as
122 viewed from the top. Each tube was numbered as an identifier. (B) The interior view of the tube.
123 The orange sphere is a peanut butter puff, glued into the tube as bait. The black arrow in this
124 panel spans the space between the tape and the bottom of the tube, referred to as the vertical
125 height of the tape in text. This black arrow corresponds to a length of approximately 22
126 millimeters. Notice that the semi-circle area above the main opening is also taped to prevent
127 mice from exiting without crawling under the tape, and to keep debris out of the tube. (C) A hair
128 tube as viewed from the side. The tubes are 8 inches long.

130 We employed a stratified uniform sampling strategy to maximize the representation of
131 sampled habitats in the yard; upon arrival to the yard, we stratified by habitat suitability for the
132 target species (low, medium and high) and location relative to wooded area (Supp. Table 1,

133 Supp. Figure 1). We hypothesized tubes near or in wooded locations would be utilized by
134 shrews, chipmunks, and white-footed mice whereas tubes in non-wooded locations would be
135 visited by house mice, as this species is human-adapted (Berry, 1981). We expected that the most
136 heavily used habitat by white-footed mice, chipmunks and shrews would be woody vegetation,
137 which has been shown to be highly suitable for small mammals (Dickman, 1992; Drickamer,
138 1990; Jensen et al., 2003); we hypothesized that habitat under buildings or decks would be used
139 the most often by house mice (West and Messmer, 1998). We predicted that leaf litter and open
140 spaces would be avoided by all target small mammal species (Bowers et al., 1993; Dickman,
141 1992; Drickamer, 1990; Hughes et al., 1994). Hair tubes were placed at least ten meters apart to
142 ensure independence between traps (Chiron et al. 2018). Tubes were secured with flexible metal
143 wire and collected after five days (Chiron et al. 2018). Upon collection, we removed the tape
144 from the tubes, and any sections of tape with hair attached were put into conical Falcon tubes
145 with 70% isopropyl alcohol for storage.

146 *Sample preparation and hair characteristics*

147 We examined each section of tape under a dissecting scope at 10X magnification and
148 separated hairs by type based on length, color, shape, and thickness (Figure 2). We applied
149 adhesive remover (Goo Gone Original, Weiman Products LLC) to tape samples to facilitate the
150 removal of hair with forceps. To maximize the information while minimizing processing time we
151 subsampled the hair on the tape based on the estimated number of hairs present: when 1-5 pieces
152 of one type of hair were counted on the tape, they were all removed; when ~6-20 pieces of one
153 type of hair were counted on the tape most (approximately 90 percent) were removed; when ~21-
154 50 pieces of one type of hair were counted on the tape at least three quarters were removed, and
155 when more than 50 pieces of one type of hair were counted on the tape at least half were

156 removed. We ensured that samples were taken of all hair types found on a given piece of tape.

157 All hair pieces were rinsed and saved in 100% ethanol by type.

158

159 **Figure 2. Flowchart for the visual identification of hairs.** The algorithm was developed is

160 based on comparisons to the literature, a reference hair collection and expert knowledge of

161 Staten Island fauna. See Appendix 1 and 2 for picture references.

163 We permanently mounted 3-6 randomly chosen hairs from each sample on microscope
164 slides for identification using a brightfield microscope (Echo, Revolve) at 200X, and then 400X,
165 using Cytoseal (Richard Allen Scientific) as the mounting medium. Samples containing three or
166 fewer hairs, we temporarily mounted. We collected the following data for each mounted hair:
167 color, length, width across the base, width across the mid-shaft, width across the medulla, a
168 description of the medulla, a description of the tip, and the approximate number of hairs
169 belonging to each sample (Figure 2). The mid-shaft and medulla widths were measured in
170 approximately the same location on the hair so that a medullary index could be obtained for each
171 hair by calculating the quotient of the medulla width and the mid-shaft width. We photographed
172 the base, mid-shaft, medulla, and tip of each mounted hair. We also documented helpful
173 diagnostic characteristics such as the presence of strictures and spatulate tips (Appendix 1,
174 Figure 2a). Cuticle patterns were obtained by covering individual hairs in clear glue (Elmer's
175 brand), allowing the glue to dry for approximately 25 minutes, then removing the hairs from the
176 glue and examining the pattern left in the glue under the microscope at 200X.

177 We measured the same features from reference hairs from species (target and non-target)
178 known to commonly occur on Staten Island, including Northern short tailed shrew (*Blarina*
179 *brevicauda*), white-footed mouse (*Peromyscus leucopus*), house mouse (*Mus musculus*), Eastern
180 meadow vole (*Microtus pennsylvanicus*), Eastern mole (*Scalopus aquaticus*), Eastern grey
181 squirrel (*Sciurus carolinensis*), Eastern chipmunk (*Tamias striatus*), brown rat (*Rattus*
182 *norvegicus*), Virginia opossum (*Didelphis virginiana*), raccoon (*Procyon lotor*), domestic dog
183 (*Canis familiaris*), domestic cat (*Felis catus*), and white-tailed deer (*Odocoileus virginianus*).
184 We extended our mammalian hair reference to include hairs from other species that have not
185 been reported or are rare on Staten Island: black rat (*Rattus rattus*), long-tailed weasel (*Mustela*

186 *frenata*), stoat/ermine (*Mustela erminea*), striped skunk (*Mephitis mephitis*), American mink
187 (*Neovison vison*), and fisher (*Pekania pennanti*). We based the identification of the most likely
188 species in our samples on the comparison between collected hairs and reference hairs,
189 family/genus hair descriptions (Mayer, 1952), and reports of urban small mammals in our region
190 (Mahan and O'Connell, 2005). *Peromyscus maniculatum* is less common in the study area and
191 hair morphology is very similar to *Peromyscus leucopus*, so we assumed that any hair identified
192 as *Peromyscus sp.* would most likely correspond to *Peromyscus leucopus* hair (Mayer, 1952).

193 After initial measurements were taken for all reference and hair tube samples, and all
194 possible identifications were made, we disregarded samples for which identification was unlikely
195 or unnecessary. This was the case when hairs had a nonspecific medulla pattern, there were four
196 or fewer hairs in a sample and none were able to be identified after initial measurements were
197 taken and/or the hairs were too long to belong to any of our target species. After excluding these
198 samples, we addressed any remaining samples containing unidentified hairs by bleaching with
199 3% hydrogen peroxide for a clearer view of the medullary pattern and/or obtaining casts of
200 cuticle scale patterns for comparison with reference samples.

201

202

203 *Hair identification*

204 In the absence of a hair key for small mammals in the region, we used our expert knowledge
205 and previous reports of common species in the region (Mahan and O'Connell, 2005) to prepare
206 our reference hair collection. Hair identification from the samples was conducted using key hair
207 features described at the genus order (Mayer, 1952), including width, length, color pattern,
208 presence of strictures, type of hair tip (round, spatulate tip, etc.), medulla pattern, and comparing

209 to reference hair samples. When hairs were similar regarding these features, we included the
210 cuticle pattern as a feature to confirm the species. Appendices 1 and 2 include pictures of our
211 hair sample and reference collection that show these features for all species and the
212 identification flowchart for the hair samples collected from Staten Island is depicted in Figure 2.

213 We grouped detailed medulla descriptions of reference hairs (Table 1) and sample hairs
214 (Table 2) into specific categories, and then grouped similar specific categories into broader
215 categories to reduce their number (Table 3). Descriptions of the broad categories are as follows:

- 216 • A: Hair displays ovate medullary aggregations, the maximum number of rows observed
217 is 2 or 3
- 218 • B: Hair medulla has well-formed aggregations that are not or may not be ovate
- 219 • C: Hair medulla is absent, or did not allow for identification of the hair
- 220 • D: Hair medulla shows vacuolation
- 221 • E: Hair medulla is homogenous
- 222 • F: Hair displays ovate medullary aggregations, at least 4 rows observed.

223 The meadow vole's medulla pattern was generally ovate 2-4 aggregations abreast (i.e.
224 aggregations in rows running alongside the hair), which overlaps with the medulla patterns of
225 white-footed mice (2-3 aggregations abreast) or house mice (4 aggregations abreast) (Appendix 1
226 and 2). Thus, to further distinguish from white-footed mouse hair we used the width of the hair
227 (i.e., vole hairs were thicker) and to distinguish from house mice, we use the cuticle patterns
228 (Figure 2).

229 We used cuticle patterns to differentiate between shrews and mole hair, and to confirm
230 identifications of meadow vole hairs as opposed to house mouse hairs. General description of the
231 types of cuticle patterns observed in small mammal hairs have been previously described by

232 Cavia et al. (2008). By comparing shrew and mole hairs in our reference collection, we found
233 that shrew hairs usually had singular scales across the width of hairs at the thickest point whereas
234 mole hairs had multiple scales across the width of hairs at the thickest point (Appendix 1). This
235 allowed us to confirm the insectivore hairs we obtained in hair tubes belonged to shrews rather
236 than moles (Appendix 2). Both Cavia et al. (2008) and our reference collection demonstrated that
237 house mouse hair cuticle scale patterns are diamond-shaped with pointed or semi-pointed tips
238 (Appendix 1). This distinctive pattern is different from the meadow vole scale pattern, consisting
239 of wide, thin, rectangular scales and smooth edges (Appendices 1 and 2). The cuticle scale
240 patterns on these hairs are the main difference, as the medulla patterns, widths, lengths, and
241 spatulate tips are all similar between the hairs of the two species.

242 Finally, chipmunk hair was identified based on two characteristics: color pattern and
243 medulla pattern (Figure 2). However, we cannot completely distinguish between chipmunk and
244 squirrel hair as they both have similar hair measurements and medulla patterns (both belonging
245 to the Sciuridae family). However, squirrel hairs in the reference collections were longer and the
246 color banding did not match the pattern observed in the hairs collected in the field, which were
247 more similar to the chipmunk reference hair banding. Thus, we concluded that were most likely
248 chipmunk hair. However, we also collected hairs that were darker and did not match the
249 chipmunk color banding but matched the chipmunk hair length. The latter could be from another
250 species in the Sciuridae family based on the similar medulla pattern.

251 *Data analyses*

252 In order to evaluate the performance of the hair identification protocol using hair
253 measurements and medulla pattern as key features for identification (hereafter, “visual
254 identification”), we used Factor Analysis of Mixed Data (FAMD) to explore the association

255 between numerical and categorical variables that were used to characterize the hairs
256 (Kassambara, 2017). Moreover, as with any principal component method, FAMDs summarize
257 the dataset comprised of correlated variables (hair features) in independent dimensions, and each
258 individual observation (each individual hair) is described by their coordinates. This information
259 can then be used by classification algorithms to predict the grouping of individuals.

260 We conducted a FAMD using the broad medullae categories hair lengths, width of
261 medullae, width at the mid-shaft, and the medullary index using the reference hairs as a training
262 dataset for the model. The predicted coordinate values for each dimension were obtained for the
263 reference hairs, as well as the hair samples collected using the hair traps (unknown origin, for
264 which we conducted the visual identification) which we used as a test dataset for out-of-sample
265 predictions. This allowed us to summarize the information and use these coordinates in a K-
266 Nearest Neighbor Classification model to predict the species identity of the sample hairs (test
267 dataset) based on the reference hairs' identity and hair features (training dataset). We compared
268 the identity of the hair sample of unknown origin predicted by the KNN model using hair
269 measures and medulla pattern with the visual identification carried out using the flowchart on
270 Figure 2 using a heatmap to visualize the proportional 2-way table. All analyses were conducted
271 in R (R core team, 2013), using the FactorMineR package (Le et al, 2020).

272 *Ethic statement*

273 Our protocol complies with the methods and criteria in our field (ecology) regarding the
274 trapping of animals and follows the guidelines of the American Society of Mammalogists (Sikes
275 et al, 2016). This field protocol was approved by the Columbia University Institutional Review
276 Board (IRB protocol #AAAS9019) and Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC
277 protocol #AAAW0454).

278 **RESULTS**

279 A total of 4048 residents were called using a phone list and of the residents called, 105
280 completed our epidemiological phone survey (2.5% of the calls made resulted in surveys taken).
281 Of those residents, 66 were willing to facilitate us visiting their homes (62.9% acceptability rate).
282 We deployed a total of 755 hair tubes in 59 yards during the study period (89.4% compliance
283 rate). The median number of tubes deployed per yard was 11 (interquartile range = 7). Hair
284 samples were collected from 254 tubes (34%); 9% contained multiple types of hair. Less than
285 5% (35) of the tubes were not recovered. Of the 254 tubes containing hair, 130 tubes contained at
286 least one unidentified hair, although unidentified and identified hairs occurred together in 90 of
287 these tubes. Six hair types were identified: 98 contained white-footed mouse hair, 16 contained
288 shrew hair, 76 contained raccoon hair (non-target), 35 contained chipmunk hair, 8 contained vole
289 hair (not further analyzed), and 21 contained pet hair (non-target).

290 The six hair features considered in the FAMD analysis resulted in 5 dimensions, of which
291 the first three dimensions accounted for ~70% of explained variance and increased to 85% when
292 including the fourth dimension (Supp. Figure 2). Thus, we used the predicted coordinates of
293 dimensions 1-4 in the classification model. Approximately 85 percent of the first dimension was
294 composed of medulla width, mid-shaft width, and broad medulla category (Supp. Figure 3).
295 Medulla broad category, hair length, and medullary index comprised approximately 95 percent
296 of the second dimension (Supp. Figure 3). Broad medulla category contributed to 90 percent of
297 the third dimension three and 100 percent of the fourth dimension (Supp. Figure 3). Our
298 identification of sample hairs and the predicted identification were the same approximately 85
299 percent of the time for white-footed mice, short-tailed shrews, and voles (Figure 3). However, for

300 chipmunks, predicted and visual identification was the same only 25 percent of the time (Figure
 301 3). Non-target species identification was less reliable (Figure 3)

302 **Figure 3. Heatmap of the predicted species by the K-nearest neighbor model vs. the visual**
 303 **identification using the flowchart.** The number inside of each square corresponds to the
 304 proportion of outcomes in which a predicted and visual species identification for hairs matched,
 305 e.g., “0.86” in the first row and first column position means that 86% of hairs identified visually
 306 as *Peromyscus* (white-footed mouse) hairs, were also predicted by the classification algorithm as
 307 belonging to white-footed mice. Pet hair category refers mostly to domestic dog hair.

309 **DISCUSSION**

310 In this study, we show an inexpensive and non-invasive way for identifying small
311 mammal species occurring in urban yards. Observations of relevant reference hairs in our
312 collection were generally consistent with those in previously published keys or atlases.
313 Nonetheless, some differences were observed. For example, Debelica et al. (2009) found that the
314 medullary index of Virginia opossum guard hair was upwards of 0.5, while we observed a lower
315 medullary index of 0.4 in these hairs, although we examined a very small sample size. These
316 authors also published a description of the white-footed mouse medulla stating that the medulla
317 contains ovate aggregations in two columns (Debelica et al., 2009), however, we found that one
318 or three columns were commonly observed in thinner or thicker than average hairs of our
319 reference hairs, respectively. The description of hairs of *Peromyscus* species in Mayer (1952)
320 states the minimum length is 9 millimeters and the minimum width is 33 micrometers. We found
321 that the average length of *Peromyscus* hair in our reference collection was approximately 7.25
322 millimeters and the minimum width was 14 micrometers. These deviances can be explained
323 when one considers that keys and atlases must provide generalized descriptions that often
324 exclude outlying observations or do not capture the full range. Mayer (1952) acknowledges this
325 in the introductory section of his study and encourages the reader to allow for flexibility in the
326 measurements he provides when utilizing his key for their own identifications. Thus, a reference
327 hair collection is advised.

328 We verified the need for a reference collection to effectively identify hairs (Mayer, 1952;
329 Tridico et al., 2014). Final identifications were more difficult to obtain with guides, atlases, or
330 keys than with reference collections. Reference samples enable comparisons between a hair of an
331 unknown type and a hair of a known type, and help validate our visual identifications.

332 Additionally, descriptions in dichotomous keys can be poorly defined, or based on characteristics
333 that are not plausible to obtain for every user. For example, cross sections of hairs are used in
334 identification (see Mayer, 1952), however, the high number, short length, and extreme fragility
335 of many of our collected samples made this metric unusable in our study.

336 Variables included in the FAMD analysis were chosen because they have been previously
337 validated as legitimate metrics for morphological hair identification ((Debelica et al., 2009;
338 Mayer, 1952; Normandeau et al., 2018; Tridico et al., 2014). Predicted identifications obtained
339 for sample hairs using a FAMD analysis of reference hair measurements were relatively
340 consistent with visual identifications we made for white-footed mice, short-tailed shrews, and
341 voles (Figure 3). However, there was far less consistency between predicted and visual
342 identification of chipmunk hair (Figure 3). We explain this observation in two ways. First, many
343 chipmunk guard hairs in our reference collection had four distinct color bands along their
344 lengths: a white base, followed by alternating bands of orange and black (Figure 2). Squirrel
345 hairs had similar banding however the number of color bands was variable, and the white base
346 was absent. Therefore, color was a helpful identifier for chipmunk hair, but not for hairs of other
347 species, and color was not included as a variable in the FAMD. Without the inclusion of color
348 information, the predictions from the FAMD should be somewhat different from the visual
349 identifications we made. Furthermore, ermine and fisher were the only other dominant species
350 predictions for hair we identified as chipmunk but neither of these species are known to be
351 present on Staten Island.

352 The main limitation of this study is that hair characteristics can vary within a single
353 species, and even within an individual (Moore, 1988). For example, the width of a hair impacts
354 the formation of cuticle scales and the medulla (Smith, 1933). As stated above these are used as

355 diagnostic features when identifying hairs, so hairs of different widths belonging to the same
356 species may look different. Further, hairs on different parts of the body also have variable
357 morphologies (Mathiak, 1938). Fur hairs (insulating hairs) which lie below guard hairs are
358 significantly more variable in their morphological structure between individuals of the same
359 species and therefore are not used for identification (Normandeau et al., 2018). While hair traps
360 are more likely to obtain guard hair samples, we cannot discard the presence of fur hairs. We
361 believe that many of the hairs we were unable to identify were fur hairs. In this study,
362 unidentified hairs were most often found in the same tube as identified hairs, as opposed to being
363 the only hairs in a tube. Further, we were unable to group unidentified hairs as a single type of
364 hair. These observations are consistent with both fur hairs and guard hairs being collected in
365 tubes, and only guard hairs received subsequent identification. Thus, we assert that most
366 unidentified hairs in this study were probably fur hairs, not guard hairs.

367 Our traps were targeted for mice and similar size mammals; hence the openings were 22
368 millimeters high (Chiron et al., 2018), however, it is possible we obtained paw or nose hair from
369 larger animals interested in the bait. We believe this occurred with raccoon hair collected in our
370 hair tubes. Moreover, we placed our tubes in yards, meaning pets had access and dog hair
371 morphologies vary with the breed (Tumiłowicz et al., 2018; Vaishnav et al., 2021), making
372 identification of dog hair challenging with only hair from two breeds of dog in our reference
373 collection. These non-target species can further complicate hair identification of targeted species.
374 Lastly, given our collection methods, broken hairs were common. When hairs break, the
375 medullary index is still an appropriate diagnostic character (Normandeau et al., 2018), but cuticle
376 scales and medullae patterns, vary along the length of each hair (Mathiak, 1938; Tridico et al.,
377 2014).

378 There are two other important considerations resulting specifically from the hair tube
379 methodology we utilized in this study. The first is that hair tubes are not species-specific,
380 meaning a wide range of hair types can be collected even when controlling for the opening
381 height, making identification more challenging due to an increased number of possibilities. The
382 second is that contamination between samples was limited, but still possible. When collecting
383 tubes, we placed them into boxes such that two given tubes would be side by side, but never end
384 to end. We also sealed the boxes until tape could be removed from the tubes to prevent hair from
385 entering the tubes after collection.

386 Hair morphology proved to be a valuable technique for monitoring the distribution of
387 small mammals, especially when live trapping is logistically difficult (e.g., urban yards). High
388 acceptability and compliance rate by homeowners and recovery of more than 95% of the hair
389 tubes indicate that is a suitable method in these settings. To our knowledge, there is no hair
390 morphology description for the species in urban areas in the Northeast U.S, this study may assist
391 in other studies using hair identification for mammal species monitoring.

392

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472

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473 **Table 1.** General descriptions and measurements of reference hairs belonging to each species.

Species	Length (mm) (maximum, average)	Shaft width (nm) (range, average)	Medulla width (nm) (range, average)	Medullary index (range, average)	Medulla description	Medulla broad category
White-footed mouse (<i>Peromyscus sp.</i>)	13, 7.235	14-45, 27.76	6-39, 21.12	0.4-0.9286, 0.7232	Ovate aggregations 1-3 abreast, almost entire shaft width, aggregations can be fused	A
Mouse mouse (<i>Mus musculus</i>)	7, 5.667	38-43, 40.67	25-37, 31.33	0.6098-0.9737, 0.7759	Ovate aggregations 2-4 abreast, almost entire shaft width, aggregations can be fused	A or F
Northern short tailed shrew (<i>Blarina brevicauda</i>)	6, 5.7	17-30, 24.30	10-24, 16.8	0.5-0.8276, 0.6736	Wide, rectangular aggregations, never in multiple columns, almost entire shaft width	B
Eastern mole (<i>Scalopus aquaticus</i>)	7, 5.909	24-44, 32.36	16-28, 23	0.6136-0.8065, 0.7186	Wide, rectangular aggregations, never in multiple columns, almost entire shaft width	B
Eastern meadow vole	13, 10	22-60, 45	7-49, 32.5	0.3182-0.8333, 0.6743	Ovate aggregations 4-6 abreast,	A, B or F

<i>(Microtus pennsylvanicus)</i>					almost entire midshaft width	
Brown rat <i>(Rattus norvegicus)</i>	21, 17.33	59-80, 67.67	36-53, 42.67	0.5625- 0.6625, 0.661	wide, thin aggregations , very dark	B or E
Black rat <i>(Rattus rattus)</i>	12, 7.786	14-137, 49.57	6-122, 40.86	0.4286-0.918, 0.7368	Juvenile hairs display circular aggregations 3-6 across; adult hairs usually display 8 circular aggregations across however underfurs of both stages have 1-2 aggregations	A, B or F
Eastern chipmunk <i>(Tamias striatus)</i>	19, 12.09	55-94, 71.36	40-78, 57.36	0.6557- 0.8769, 0.7971	Dark column, 4-5 circular or ovular vacuolations abreast, almost entire shaft width -sometimes appears like ovate aggs.	D or F
Eastern grey squirrel <i>(Sciurus carolinensis)</i>	15, 10.40	41-94, 68.50	30-82, 53.6	0.6056- 0.8723, 0.7747	Dark column, 4-8 circular or ovular vacuolations abreast,	D or F

					almost entire shaft width -sometimes appears like ovate aggs.	
Domestic cat (<i>Felis catus</i>),	40, 21.5	27-76, 50	8-57, 31	0.2963-0.75, 0.5729	Dark column, 1-2 wide, thin vacuolations abreast	B
Domestic dog (<i>Canis familiaris</i>)	57, 52	83-108, 97	44-67, 58	0.5301-0.63, 0.5935	Homogenous, dark column	D
Virginia opossum (<i>Didelphis virginiana</i>)*	50 and 48	91 and 98	37 and 38	0.3878 and 0.4066	Appears vacuolated and ridged? Or irregular aggregations	D
Raccoon (<i>Procyon lotor</i>),*	45 and 46	93	46 and 47	0.4946 and 0.5054	Homogenous, dark column, approximately half of the shaft width	E
Long-tailed weasel (<i>Mustela frenata</i>)	18, 12.6	69-91, 80.6	49-72, 61.4	0.7024- 0.8415, 0.7597	irregular, aggregations wide and thin, varying numbers across	B
Stoat/Ermine (<i>Mustela erminea</i>)	10, 7	60-99, 79	46-83, 59.89	0.6986- 0.8384, 0.7548	vacuolations of irregular size and shape, usually oval or circular, 4-5 across	B

Striped skunk (<i>Mephitis mephitis</i>)*	77, one length unmeasured	108 and 112	76 and 38	0.7037 and 0.3393	Homogenous, dark column	E
American mink (<i>Neovision vison</i>)*	26 and 28	86 and 91	47 and 53	0.5465 and 0.5824	wide thin aggregations displaying occasional bulges	B
Fisher (<i>Pekania pennanti</i>)*	37 and 34	76 and 67	42 and 41	0.5526 and 0.6119	wide thin aggregations displaying occasional bulges	B

474 *Only two guard hairs examined for these species so individual measurements reported rather
475 than averages.

476

477 **Table 2.** General descriptions and measurements of sample hairs belonging to each species based
 478 on our visual identifications.

Visual Identification	Length (mm) (maximum, average)	Shaft width (nm) (range, average)	Medulla width (nm) (range, average)	Medullary index (range, average)	Medulla description	Medulla broad category
White-footed mouse (<i>Peromyscus sp.</i>)	15, 7.261	8-57, 26.16	6-41, 18.12	0.2143-1.0, 0.6878	Ovate aggregations 1-3 abreast, almost entire shaft width, aggregations can be fused	A, B, or F
Northern short tailed shrew (<i>Blarina brevicauda</i>)	10, 5.167	13-43, 23.56	6-27, 14.25	0.2558-0.7941, 0.6130	Wide, rectangular aggregations, never in multiple columns, almost entire shaft width	A or B
Eastern chipmunk (<i>Tamias striatus</i>)	10, 4.451	25-120, 74.42	8-97, 48.93	0.1481-0.9315, 0.6279	Dark column, 4-5 circular or ovular vacuolations abreast, almost entire shaft width -sometimes appears like ovate aggregations	A, B, D, E or F
Eastern meadow vole (<i>Microtus pennsylvanicus</i>)	9, 6.714	38-53, 45	30-46, 37.64	0.7143-0.9149, 0.8353	Ovate aggregations 3-4 abreast, almost entire shaft width, aggregations can be fused	A or F
Raccoon (<i>Procyon lotor</i>),*	27, 7.239	10-157, 81.11	5-82, 31.83	0.1064-1.0, 0.3774	Homogenous, dark column half of shaft width or less;	B, D or E

					1 column of square or rectangular aggregations if hair is exceptionally thin	
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481 **Table 3.** Medullary descriptions and broad category assignments for each medullary type. We
 482 grouped detailed medulla descriptions into specific categories considering the presence of
 483 aggregations, their types, number of rows and other distinctive features. We then grouped similar
 484 specific categories into broader categories based on similarities.

485

General Medulla Description	Specific category	Broad category
Homogenous	A	E
Irregular, ovular or circular vacuolations	B	D
Medulla absent or barely present	C	C
Medulla pattern not visible	D	C
One row of aggregations	E	B
Ovate aggregations, mix of 1 and 2 rows at thickest section	F	A
Ovate aggregations, 2 rows at thickest section	G	A
Ovate aggregations, mix of 2 and 3 rows at thickest section	H	A
Ovate aggregations, 3 rows at the thickest section	I	A
Ovate aggregations, mix of 3 and 4 rows at thickest section	J	F
Ovate aggregations, 4 rows at thickest section	K	F
Ovate aggregations, mix of 4 and 5 rows at thickest section	L	F
Ovate aggregations, 5 rows at thickest section	M	F
Ovate aggregations, mix of 5 and 6 rows at thickest section	N	F
Vacuolations, wide and thin rather than circular or ovular	O	D
Wide and thin aggregations with a mixture of 1 or 2 rows	P	B
Irregular vacuolation, no specific shape	Q	D
Multiple types described, not helpful for identification	R	C
Ovate aggregations, 8 or more rows at thickest section	S	F
Ovate aggregations, 6 rows at thickest section	T	F
Ovate aggregations, mix of 3-5 rows at thickest section	U	F
Black lines (due to pigmentation) running lengthwise in hair.	Z	C

486

487 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

488 **Supp. Table 1.** Habitat suitability categories associated with hair tube placement.

489 **Supp. Figure 1.** Locations of tubes within a parcel belonging to either of our locational classes.

490 The orange arrows represent hair tube locations we would consider to be non-wooded. The
491 yellow flower represents an ornamental plant. The purple arrows indicate hair tube locations we
492 designated as wooded. Wooded locations could be both inside or outside of a parcel.

493 **Supp. Figure 2.** Percentage of total variance explained by each dimension obtained from the
494 Factor Analysis of Mixed Data. The total variance in the sample among all variables measured
495 can be summarized by independent dimensions, in this case dim 1-4 summarize ~85% of the
496 total variance in the sample.

497 **Supp. Figure 3.** Relative contribution of variables in accounting for the variability (expressed in
498 percentage) in each dimension of Factor Analysis of Mixed Data.

499 **Appendix 1: Hair morphology of those collected using hair traps.** This appendix contains
500 photographs of five hair types collected in the hair tubes we deployed in Staten Island yards, at
501 200X or 400X magnification using an echo revolve brightfield microscope. The photographs
502 presented here are of hair bases, tips, medullae, and cuticle patterns.

503 **Appendix 2: Hair morphology of those from the reference collection.** This appendix contains
504 photographs of all reference hairs of small and medium sized mammals known to occur on
505 Staten Island, at 200X or 400X magnification using an echo revolve brightfield microscope. The
506 photographs presented here are of hair bases, tips, medullae, and cuticle patterns

507